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D8.1

Project Website

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Executive Summary

The website of the EU/Horizon Europe project *SP*Ecification, *AN*alysis & *RE*-calibration of *HI*gh Energy *PA*ricle *DA*ta (SPEARHEAD) was released at spearhead-he.eu. The site is based on a WordPress system and is being hosted at the National Data Center (NDC) cloud academic service of Greece while being developed and maintained by the National Observatory of Athens (NOA). The website contains a landing page and separate sections for: *Project*, *Partners*, *EAC*, *News*, and *Contact*. The landing page (*Home*) contains a shorter version of the public project abstract that is also available in the [Cordis site](#) of the project. The *Project* and *Partners* sections provide some further basic information on the project and short descriptions of the beneficiaries. The *News* section contains recent highlights and events that can be linked via, e.g., the project's social media accounts. To this end, *facebook*, *instagram* and *X* accounts have been implemented for the effective dissemination and communication of the project. Those are further linked through the project's website. The *Contact* section provides an interface to ask questions or leave comments on the website and on the project.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary *iii*

1 Introduction **1**

2 SPEARHEAD’s website..... **2**

 2.1 The website..... 2

 2.2 Social media 6

3 Conclusions **8**

List of Acronyms/Abbreviations **9**

List of Figures

FIGURE 1-1 – DISTRIBUTION OF SPEARHEAD’S PARTNERS..... 1

FIGURE 2-1 – HOME PAGE OF SPEARHEAD..... 2

FIGURE 2-2 – THE ABOUT PAGE OF SPEARHEAD 3

FIGURE 2-3 – THE PARTNERS PAGE OF SPEARHEAD 3

FIGURE 2-4 – EXAMPLE OF THE DETAILS PROVIDED FOR EACH PARTNER (HERE THE EXAMPLE PRESENTS NOA) 4

FIGURE 2-5 – THE EXTERNAL ADVISORY COMMITTEE (EAC) PAGE OF SPEARHEAD 4

FIGURE 2-6 – THE CONTACT PAGE OF SPEARHEAD 5

FIGURE 2-7 – THE NEWS PAGE OF SPEARHEAD 5

FIGURE 2-8 – THE SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS OF SPEARHEAD (CLOCKWISE DIRECTION: FACEBOOK, INSTAGRAM, X) 6

FIGURE 2-9 – THE BUFFER AND THE META BUSINESS SUITE OF SPEARHEAD..... 7

1 Introduction

The project *SPeCification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data* (SPEARHEAD) is a 3 year-long Research and Innovation action funded by the Horizon Europe framework programme of the European Union (EU). It has eight partners from six European countries (Figure 1-1).

Figure 1-1 – Distribution of SPEARHEAD's Partners

The SPEARHEAD project focuses on high energy particles, originating either from the Sun (i.e., Solar Energetic Particles – SEPs) or our Galaxy (Galactic Cosmic Rays – GCRs). SPEARHEAD will address several open scientific questions on the acceleration, release and propagation physical processes of such particles. In doing so, SPEARHEAD provides novel high-level data products based on recalibrations of radiation monitor data -- on so-far unreleased data from science-grade instruments, and measurements of ground-based neutron monitors; technical notes on the response functions of several science-grade and monitoring instruments, utilising Geant4 modelling; comprehensive catalogues of near-relativistic ions and relativistic electrons in strong SEP/GLE events as well as FD events from a fleet of different instruments onboard spacecraft, at radial distances from 0.04 to 5 AU; scientific and data analysis as well as tools enabling the coordinated analysis of high energy particle data with contexts observations.

The project started on **1 January 2024**. The public website of the project was released on the second month of the project at spearhead-he.eu. This document briefly introduces the website, which is **Deliverable D8.1** of the project, together with several communication channels (i.e. social media) that have been implemented.

2 SPEARHEAD's website

A summary of the developments with respect to the project's website and communication channels follows:

2.1 The website

The National Observatory of Athens (NOA) hosts and maintains the SPEARHEAD project's public website, which was constructed using the WordPress system. Throughout the project, the website will be updated on a regular basis, with NOA being responsible for doing so. The website will promote the initiative by outlining its objectives and partner backgrounds. The website's goal is to provide information about the project to both specialized and general audiences. The project's Dissemination and Communication Plan will provide an overview of dissemination activities and timeframes. The goal is to have all of the partners contribute to the News area with outcomes and events. We will also collect statistics on site visits.

- The website has a landing page with sections: About, Partners, EAC, Contact and News. The landing page (Home; Figure 2-1) offers a visualization of the inner heliosphere with key missions orbiting (like e.g. Solar Orbiter), providing context for the project.
- The About part (Figure 2-2) gives fundamental information about the project, such as the science questions and the technical objectives.
- The Partners (Figure 2-3) tab of the website provides a tree that gives access to brief information concerning each of the Partners (see an example in Figure 2-4).
- The EAC page (Figure 2-5) provides the External Advisory Committee (hence, EAC) members and gives links to their CVs/personal pages.
- The Contact (Figure 2-6) section includes an interface for contacting the project with questions or suggestions.
- Finally, the website's News (Figure 2-7) section contains News items, which are entries on recent project highlights (e.g., publications, deliverables) and events (e.g., meetings, new solar energetic particle events).

Figure 2-1 – Home page of SPEARHEAD

Figure 2-2 – The About page of SPEARHEAD

Figure 2-3 – The Partners page of SPEARHEAD

Figure 2-4 – Example of the details provided for each Partner (here the example presents NOA)

Figure 2-5 – The External Advisory Committee (EAC) page of SPEARHEAD

Figure 2-6 – The Contact page of SPEARHEAD

Figure 2-7 – The News page of SPEARHEAD

2.2 Social media

Communication channels through dedicated social media accounts in *facebook*, *instagram* and *X* have been established (Figure 2-8) in order to facilitate direct communication of the project’s outputs and news to a wider audience. These are directly linked at the footer of the project’s website and appear under every page. Furthermore, the posted News can be linked to the project’s various social media accounts.

Figure 2-8 – The social media channels of SPEARHEAD (clockwise direction: facebook, instagram, X)

To this end, social media administration tools like *Buffer* and *Meta Business Suite* have been implemented in the back-end of the website of the project (Figure 2-9).

Figure 2-9 – The Buffer and the Meta Business Suite of SPEARHEAD

3 Conclusions

The **Public Website** of the *SPEARHEAD project* was released at spearhead-he.eu in February 2024 and constitutes **Deliverable 8.1** of the Project.

List of Acronyms/Abbreviations

Acronym/ Abbreviation	Description
EU	European Union
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data